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Heavy metal nanopolymer sensors; The beginning of a new era in identification methods

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Abstract

Until a few decades ago, there was a general feeling that nature could automatically effectively dispose of hazardous substances and solve this problem. Although human beings today pay more attention to their environment, environmental pollution is still a global problem. Researchers estimate that industrial processes generally introduce up to one million different pollutants into the atmosphere and ecosystem of aquatic organisms. Heavy metals are one of these substances, although not all of them are harmful to humans.

Water is also a vital and scarce resource; therefore, the quality of drinking water is of great importance for human consumption. Therefore, it is obvious that the development of simple, fast and cheap methods to measure the optimal quality of drinking water and other uses is one of the important issues in the use of nanotechnology.

Keywords: Nanosensor, Polymer composites, Optical sensor, Heavy metals